

Unveiling the drivers of portfolio equity and bond investment in the European Union: The interplay of tax havens and gravity factors*

Mariam Camarero [†], Alejandro Muñoz [‡] and Cecilio Tamarit ^{a§}

Abstract

This paper examines the drivers of cross-border portfolio allocation within the EU and between EU countries and the rest of the world from 2007 to 2017, using a structural asset trade gravity framework. Relying on a dataset that corrects for distortions caused by tax havens through a remapping of portfolio positions based on the nationality principle, we estimate a model in which financial frictions are captured through bilateral and multilateral resistance terms. Our results show that gravity variables perform as expected: distance reduces holdings, while economic size and historical ties promote cross-border investment. A significant EU effect emerges only for bonds, suggesting the presence of a home bias. In contrast, equity holdings appear more globally diversified and sensitive to financial frictions. Comparisons with residence-based data confirm that failing to account for tax haven intermediation weakens model fit and biases key estimates. The results are robust across estimation methods and outperform traditional gravity models for goods trade. These findings highlight the importance of adjusting for offshore financial centers when analyzing international asset flows.

Keywords: Gravity, cross-border asset holdings; global frictions; international finance.

JEL classification: F36; F41; G11; G15.

*The authors acknowledge the comments and guidance of the EER editor, Stefania Garetto, the associate editor and two anonymous reviewers. This paper benefited from comments by P. Anaya, N. Bogdan, JLL. Carrion-i-Silvestre, J. Crespo-Cuaresma, T. Del Barrio, A. Montanes, M. Rochina, A. Tsopanakis, Y. Yotov and attendees to the 26th INFER AC, Crete, 2024, CFE-CMStatistics 2024, King's College, London, VIII Jornadas Internacionalización, U. Nebrija, Madrid, 2025, 29th ICMAIC-2025, University of Crete, Rethymno, XXVIII AEM-University of Murcia 2025, XXVI CIE-AEEFI, UJI, Castellón, 2025. The authors acknowledge the funding from the AEI-Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities (PID2023-150095NB-C42/ AEI 10.13039 / 501100011033) and the Valencian Generalitat (PROMETEO CIPROM/2022/50). Finally, M. Camarero and C. Tamarit acknowledge the financial the EU, ERASMUS-JMO-2022-CHAIR 101083430 and project GEaR-EU - 101234793, respectively. The European Commission's support does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. All remaining errors are ours.

[†]University Jaume I and INTECO, Department of Economics, Campus de Riu Sec, E-12071 Castellón (Spain). ORCID: 0000-0003-4525-5181

[‡]University of València, Department of Applied Economics II, Av. dels Tarongers, s/n Eastern Department Building E-46022 Valencia, (Spain).

^{a§}Corresponding author: University of València and INTECO, Department of Applied Economics II, Av. dels Tarongers, s/n Eastern Department Building E-46022 Valencia, (Spain). email: Cecilio.Tamarit@uv.es ORCID: 0000-0002-0538-9882

1 Motivation

Understanding the true patterns of international portfolio investments is crucial for evaluating financial integration and its benefits¹. However, the accurate measurement of cross-border financial integration is significantly complicated by the increasing role of tax havens in international finance.

There is a growing literature studying the pivotal role of tax havens in analyzing capital mobility in its different forms.² Recent studies have increasingly employed gravity models to understand various dimensions of tax-haven activities. Cassetta et al. (2014) and Gullo and Montalbano (2022) apply gravity models to capital flows, demonstrating the relevance of tax havens for tax evasion and money laundering activities. Fonseca et al. (2023) reveal their importance in corporate control operations, while Bricongne et al. (2023) establish links between tax havens and firm-level productivity. Similarly, Delatte et al. (2022) demonstrate how tax havens generate international investment beyond standard gravitational factors such as country size and distance, substantially affecting cross-border investment geography. Finally, Santacreu (2023) in a prominent recent study incorporates tax havens into a dynamic structural gravity equation to investigate international technology licensing determinants.

This growing body of evidence reflects a fundamental shift in global financial practices: multinational companies increasingly issue securities through cross-border affiliates in tax havens to avoid capital controls, reduce tax burdens, or access global capital markets with more favorable financial conditions or longer maturities. As a consequence, the correct assignment of the original location of the investors has become a tricky question, particularly relevant for portfolio investments. According to the 6th Edition of the Balance of Payments and International Investment Position Manual (IMF, 2009), portfolio investments (both equity and bonds) represent a distinct functional category from direct investment (FDI),³ financial derivatives,⁴ other investments and reserve assets. While portfolio investment usually has less decision power in company operational management than FDI, it provides easy access to financial markets, liquidity, and flexibility, making it particularly associated with tax haven intermediation patterns.

The European Union (EU) provides an excellent setting for studying how tax havens affect our understanding of portfolio investment patterns. According to data from the European Central Bank (ECB Committee on Financial Integration, 2022), the share of cross-border holdings in euro-denominated bonds and equities has risen steadily since the launch of the euro in 1999. For example, in 2020, cross-border holdings accounted for approximately 54% of the outstanding euro-denominated bonds and 22% of the euro-denominated equities. However, these figures may be distorted by the intermediation of tax havens, potentially masking the true patterns of financial

¹Baele et al. (2004) outline three widely accepted interrelated benefits of financial integration: higher efficiency, more growth potential, and better risk-sharing opportunities.

²Examples are, among others, Hines and Rice (1994); Desai et al. (2006); Rose and Spiegel (2007) or Hines (2010).

³Equity can be classified as FDI or portfolio. Ownership of 10 percent of the voting power of an enterprise by a non-resident investor is taken as evidence of a direct investment relationship.

⁴Other than reserves.

integration within the EU. The EU faces significant challenges in understanding and managing its financial landscape due to the concentrated intermediation activities in Ireland, Luxembourg, and the Netherlands, whose scale has grown enormously (Beck et al., 2024). These “onshore offshore financial centers” (OOFs) obscure capital allocation patterns in the Euro Area (EA), complicating the assessment of the EA as a catalyzer of financial integration and the empirical validation of theories of financial asset allocation. As hubs for investment fund intermediation and securities issuance, OOFs distort statistics by recording securities and liabilities as belonging to these jurisdictions rather than the ultimate owners or corporate parents. This misrepresentation undermines policymaking, hampers evaluations of financial integration, and obscures the role of the euro in promoting cross-border investment. Addressing these limitations is crucial for achieving the EU’s economic integration and financial stability goals.

Our paper builds on the work of Damgaard et al. (2019) and Delatte et al. (2022) to address biases in portfolio driver estimations. Damgaard et al. (2019) identify “phantom investments”, corporate shells without actual activity, which account for nearly 40% of global FDI, showing that reallocating real investments to ultimate investors significantly improves the explanatory power of the gravity model. Delatte et al. (2022) find that 40% of global assets, concentrated in six tax havens, deviate from gravity estimates. Extending these insights, we refine portfolio driver estimations by reallocating financial flows to their ultimate owners, enhancing econometric models, and understanding international financial integration. This paper assesses the drivers of portfolio equity and bond stocks in the EU’s aftermath of the Great Recession and the European debt crisis, covering the sample period 2007-2017. To the best of our knowledge, no studies jointly address drivers of portfolio investments using the gravity equation, in which resistance variables are modeled through financial restrictions, and the existence of tax havens is taken into account. This is especially true in the case of the EU.

We contribute to the literature in different respects. First, unlike most previous studies, we use a recent database put together by Coppola et al. (2021) that accounts for the role of financial intermediaries that issue assets through tax havens. Consequently, the database remaps the portfolio stock to the actual source and destination countries. This is a crucial improvement compared to traditional databases for portfolios (for example, the IMF CPIS database) built under the residence principle. Properly addressing the role of tax havens is particularly relevant for some assets with a significant presence, such as portfolio equity.

Second, another singular characteristic of this paper is that we estimate the gravity equation following a theoretical model developed explicitly for financial markets by Okawa and van Wincoop (2012). In doing so, we model bilateral and multilateral resistance with financial restrictions between the country pair and relative to the rest of the world. We provide a more comprehensive analysis of the determinants of cross-border asset trade holdings. This could help researchers and policymakers better understand the complex dynamics underlying these assets. We also perform various robustness checks to ensure our results remain robust to different model specifications.

Firstly, we use different variables to model first bilateral and multilateral resistance, and second, historical links. Secondly, from an econometric standpoint, we assess the performance of different alternative estimators (OLS, PPML and G-PPML).

Finally, as a comparison exercise, we perform the analysis using the IMF (CPIS) database built under the residence principle and compare the results with those obtained with the Coppola et al. (2021) database.⁵

Our findings shed light on four relevant aspects that significantly deepen the current understanding of international portfolio investment. First, using the nationality-based database that removes the distortions from tax-haven intermediation, we find strong support for the gravity model in both equity and bond markets. For equity investments, gravitational variables show their expected associations: negative for distance and positive for economic mass. Similarly, portfolio bonds exhibit significant gravitational effects, with distance and economic size playing particularly important roles.

Second, our analysis reveals distinct patterns in how financial restrictions affect different asset classes. For equity holdings, bilateral restrictions have a negative correlation, while multilateral restrictions (measured as financial restrictions in the rest of the world) show a positive sign. This suggests a reallocation effect: when restrictions increase globally, bilateral trade between less restricted country pairs intensifies. For bonds, while bilateral resistance maintains its negative impact, the effect of multilateral resistance is notably different, indicating that these assets respond differently to global financial conditions and can be subject to a home bias effect.

Third, we find significant differences between equity and bond investments that highlight the importance of asset-specific characteristics. Bond investments show a stronger sensitivity to distance and EU membership, suggesting a more regional focus. In contrast, equity investments display greater international mobility but higher sensitivity to global risk and multilateral restrictions. Despite these differences, both asset classes show similar associations to historical links.

Finally, our comparative analysis using the IMF CPIS database reveals crucial methodological insights. When the distorting effect of tax havens is not properly accounted for, the gravity variables show lower explanatory power, and the role of multilateral resistance blurs. These differences underscore the importance of properly addressing tax haven intermediation in understanding international portfolio allocation patterns.

These findings suggest that previous studies using residence-based data may have underestimated the importance of fundamental gravity variables in explaining international portfolio allocation, particularly when tax-haven intermediation is significant. Our results thus provide a more accurate picture of the determinants of cross-border portfolio investment patterns within the EU and globally.

⁵Although CPIS data have limitations beyond the nationality vs. residence principle (incomplete country coverage and potential self-selection bias), we believe these do not significantly affect our analysis as we can replicate the same sample used in the first exercise under the nationality principle.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents a set of stylized facts on the economic relevance of tax havens that motivate our analysis. Section 3 reviews the related literature and introduces the key features of the structural asset trade gravity model employed in the study. Section 4 describes the data, outlines the econometric methodology, and details the empirical specification. Section 5 reports and discusses the main empirical findings. Finally, Section 6 concludes.

2 The relevance of tax havens for portfolio investments: some stylized facts

The large and growing capital flows of securities have long been an essential subject for research in international finance. Yet, the literature accounting for the importance of tax havens among the motives and incentives behind these flows is relatively scarce. This is due to a lack of reliable data quantifying inflows and outflows across years and countries, and information on investors, issuers, and asset types. This situation has recently changed. Fresh articles like Damgaard et al. (2019) for the case of FDI and Coppola et al. (2021) and Beck et al. (2024) for portfolio investment provide data to document the increasing role of tax havens. These offshore centers with enormous inward and outward positions blur statistics on international investments. To solve this problem, these new databases account for offshore investment and financing vehicles in tax havens remapping from a residence to a nationality basis.

Tax havens are jurisdictions offering low or zero tax rates, light regulation, and financial secrecy, attracting individuals and firms seeking to reduce tax and regulatory burdens. According to the IMF (IMF, 2000), offshore financial centers (OFCs) are defined by: (a) a high concentration of financial institutions serving non-residents; (b) external financial positions disproportionate to domestic economic activity; and (c) the provision of low taxation, minimal regulation, and confidentiality.

The use of tax havens is driven by three main factors. First, multinational corporations, particularly those with significant intangible assets, seek to minimize tax liabilities.⁶ Second, firms in emerging markets use tax havens to access global capital markets more efficiently, benefiting from lower financing costs and longer maturities while bypassing capital controls.⁷ Third, the growing role of mutual and investment funds in cross-border portfolio flows reinforces the structural relevance of tax havens in global finance.

Outdated financial regulations in industrial countries during the 1960s and 1970s spurred the growth of offshore banking and the emergence of OFCs, or tax havens. In the early 1970s, Luxembourg attracted investors from Germany, France, and Belgium through low taxes, no withholding on nonresident income, and strict banking secrecy, features also present in the Channel Islands and the Isle of Man. By the mid-1970s, Bahrain became a key hub for oil surplus recycling via favorable banking laws and tax incentives, while the Bahamas and Cayman Islands offered similar advan-

⁶In the EU, this leads to holding structures in countries such as Ireland, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Cyprus, and Malta.

⁷Variable Interest Entities (VIEs), such as those used by Alibaba via the Cayman Islands, illustrate this strategy.

tages. In the late 1990s, the appeal of OFCs for traditional banking waned as industrial countries eased financial controls and introduced competing tax incentives, although tax-driven asset management in OFCs gained prominence. Today, offshore banking is conducted largely by affiliates of major industrial and emerging-market banks.

OFCs, increasingly referred to as investment hubs, generate significant capital flows that distort cross-border investment statistics by obscuring the true origin and destination of funds. Financial intermediaries in these jurisdictions complicate the attribution of portfolio investment, as the use of shell companies, secrecy laws, and treaty shopping often hide the ultimate source and ownership of capital. This systematic misreporting leads to an overestimation of foreign financial activity in OFCs and hampers accurate economic analysis. Despite efforts by tax authorities and international organizations to enhance transparency, these challenges persist due to the opaque nature of the global financial system. While offshore banking has long been monitored by the Basel Committee, OFCs have more recently become a focus for the FATF⁸ and OECD, given their role in enabling financial flows that resist statistical tracing and undermine anticorruption and tax enforcement efforts.

These concerns are echoed in recent research highlighting how tax havens distort global capital flow statistics. Avdjiev et al. (2016) reveal growing discrepancies between datasets based on the residence principle, and Bertaut et al. (2019), comparing U.S. TIC data⁹ by residence and nationality, argue that residence-based reporting is increasingly inadequate due to the complexity of multinational structures. Damgaard et al. (2019) estimate that around 40% of global FDI consists of phantom investment lacking economic substance, and show that reallocation to ultimate investor economies enhances explanatory power. While empirical studies on OFCs remain limited, existing work underscores their systemic role: Lane and Milesi-Ferretti (2011) emphasize the influence of small financial centers; Dharmapala (2008), Dharmapala and Hines (2009), and Rose and Spiegel (2007) examine the drivers and implications of OFCs, with the latter linking proximity to deeper domestic financial systems. Lane and Milesi-Ferretti (2018) highlight the increasing relevance of OFC-based financial intermediaries globally, a pattern also found in Asia-Pacific (Black and Munro, 2010) and North America (Torslov et al., 2023). In the EU, small centers as Luxembourg, Ireland, and Malta play a key role in fund management and securitization, complicating the identification of Euro Area portfolio holders (Milesi-Ferretti et al., 2010).

We now examine the stylized facts and the role of tax havens in shaping global and EU portfolio markets. This overview highlights their systemic relevance in international finance.

Figure 1, based on IMF CPIS data under the residence principle, shows the share of tax havens¹⁰ in global portfolio equity and bonds from 2001 to 2020. Several trends stand out: (i) the share of tax

⁸The FATF (Financial Action Task Force) is an intergovernmental body established in 1989 that sets international standards to combat money laundering, terrorist financing, and other threats to the integrity of the international financial system.

⁹The Treasury International Capital (TIC) reporting system is the U.S. government's source of data on capital flows into and out of the United States, excluding direct investment, and the resulting levels of cross-border claims and liabilities.

¹⁰Classified in Table A3.

havens in equity markets has steadily risen, reaching 35%, with an acceleration post-2008; (ii) their share in bonds initially rose but declined after the financial crisis due to its debt-driven nature; and (iii) tax havens are more prominent in equity, as sovereign and corporate bond issuance is generally not intermediated via OFCs.¹¹

Figure 2 focuses on the EU, highlighting the share held by recognized EU tax havens—Cyprus, Ireland, Luxembourg, Malta, and the Netherlands. Although Belgium is not officially classified as a tax haven, it plays a similar role: in 2021, its portfolio investment assets reached \$1.2 trillion (230% of GDP), and FDI stocks amounted to \$630 billion in 2020, up to a 120% of GDP (UNCTAD, 2024).¹²

Though not always formally labeled as tax havens, these financial hubs function as conduits between capital origin and destination and are considered as OOFs (Beck et al., 2024). Their share in portfolio equity has risen to 65%, while their share in portfolio bonds remains stable between 18–22%. These patterns affirm the enduring role of tax havens within the EU.

We next disaggregate EU investment patterns in equity and bonds, distinguishing between Euro Area (EA) and non-EA countries.¹³ Table 1 shows that EU countries, with the UK as an exception (26%), primarily invest within the EU. Column two confirms a high concentration of equity investment within the EA (80–90%), except for Denmark and Sweden.

Figure 3 (left) presents portfolio EU equity allocation by issuer under the nationality principle. The U.S. is the leading destination (22%), followed by Germany, France, the UK, and Ireland. Eleven countries account for 78% of total equity investment. The right-hand chart, using IMF CPIS data under the residence principle, shows a similar pattern but highlights key discrepancies: Luxembourg, which receives 20% of total investment under the residence principle, plays no role under the nationality principle, revealing the importance of reassigning tax haven-issued assets to ultimate destinations. The presence of other OFCs (e.g., Cayman Islands) and the relative decline of Germany and France further underscore the intermediating role of Luxembourg.

Figure 4 presents similar data for portfolio EU bonds. Under the nationality principle (left chart), bonds are largely allocated within the EU, especially within the EA. Germany is the primary recipient, with the U.S. holding a comparable share. Six countries account for 59% of bond investment. Under the residence principle (right chart), the U.S. and several tax havens (Netherlands, Ireland, Luxembourg) gain weight, while final destinations often include Germany, France, Italy, and Spain.

Overall, cross-border portfolio investment in the EU exhibits a persistent regional bias,¹⁴ with the UK as a notable exception: investing more outside than within the EU, particularly in equities. For portfolio bonds, intra-EU bias is declining, suggesting gradual diversification beyond the region.

¹¹E.g., Germany cannot issue sovereign bonds through a Cayman affiliate.

¹²Brussels attracts significant Chinese FDI—averaging \$2.5 billion annually from 2010 to 2020—supported by tax incentives such as the “notional interest deduction.”

¹³Non-EA members include Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Sweden, and the UK. All but Denmark (and formerly the UK) are expected to adopt the euro upon meeting convergence criteria.

¹⁴See Section 3 for related literature.

In conclusion, empirical data suggest that tax havens play an important role in cross-border capital allocation in the EU. However, the challenge of gathering accurate and reliable data on cross-border investment flows remains a crucial issue in this area of research, and their inclusion in asset allocation modeling depicts new avenues for empirical research.

3 Empirical Models of Portfolio Investment: Literature review and theoretical foundation

The literature on portfolio investment determinants has evolved significantly, shifting from early push-pull models to the more empirically robust gravity framework. This section reviews this transition, highlighting methodological advances in explaining cross-border capital flows.

Initial studies relied on push-pull frameworks, attributing investment flows to a limited set of factors (e.g., interest rate differentials, growth disparities, and political stability). Although informative, these models were reductionist, offering limited explanatory power due to their narrow variable scope (Koepke, 2019). In response to these limitations, the gravity model gained traction, providing a richer framework that accounts for economic size and geographic proximity as core determinants of bilateral investment. Unlike the push-pull approach, the gravity model reflects the structural interconnectedness of financial markets and better captures observed investment patterns (Portes and Rey, 2005; Coeurdacier and Martin, 2009). We adopt this framework in our empirical analysis, given its demonstrated ability to explain the distribution of global portfolio investment more accurately.

3.1 Push-pull models

The push-pull framework emerged in the early 1990s to explain the drivers of international capital flows, particularly in developing economies. It distinguishes between external "push" factors from source countries and internal "pull" factors from recipient economies, even if not grounded in formal economic theory. As noted in Koepke (2019), this distinction aligns with modern portfolio theory, where diversification decisions hinge on expected returns and risk.

Empirically, the capital flow surges of the 1980s and 1990s, especially in Latin America, spurred early research. Seminal contributions such as Calvo et al. (1993, 1996) and Fernandez-Arias (1996) examined whether these flows were driven by unfavorable conditions in developed countries (push) or attractive features of recipient economies (pull).¹⁵ These studies largely emphasized push factors. Later work, such as Caballero et al. (2008) and Mendoza et al. (2009), introduced more sophisticated risk frameworks that further explored the weight of internal pull dynamics.

Common push variables include global risk aversion, interest rates, and output growth in source (often advanced) economies. Pull factors typically encompass domestic output growth, asset returns, and country risk. Numerous empirical studies have applied this taxonomy. Koepke (2019),

¹⁵For instance, high domestic interest rates or a developed financial system act as pull factors, while foreign investors seeking diversification represent a push dynamic.

in a survey focused on emerging markets, finds global risk aversion and external interest rates to be the main drivers of equity and bond flows, while pull factors matter more for banking flows.

The framework remains highly influential, particularly in the aftermath of the global financial crisis. Sarno et al. (2016) extend the analysis to U.S. capital outflows toward 55 countries and find that push factors account for approximately 80% of the variation in flows. Koepke and Paetzold (2020) update the literature to cover 88 studies, confirming the dominant role of push variables for portfolio flows, though mixed effects are observed across flow types and frequencies. Lopez and Stracca (2021) further shows that, in the post-COVID context, global factors and shifts in risk appetite remain central, with the traditional divide between advanced and emerging markets increasingly blurred.

3.2 A gravity approach to cross-border asset mobility

Gravity models, long used in Economics to explain trade flows, posit that trade volume is proportional to the product of economic sizes and inversely proportional to the distance between countries. These models have been successfully adapted to cross-border asset flows, including equities and bonds, offering a robust framework for analyzing international financial transactions, even before their formal theoretical foundation was established.

Since the 1990s, gravity models have been increasingly applied to portfolio investment. Portes and Rey (1998) demonstrate their relevance for financial co-movements, while the first formal model for financial assets was proposed by Martin and Rey (2004) and later extended by Coeurdacier and Martin (2009) to Arrow-Debreu securities with transaction costs.¹⁶ Two contributions by Rey link the push-pull and gravity literature. Hau and Rey (2006) develop a structural model of capital allocation, highlighting the role of geographic and cultural proximity in portfolio diversification. Portes and Rey (2005) apply a gravity model to bilateral gross equity flows (1989–1996), emphasizing market size and transaction costs, while finding weaker support for pure diversification motives. Similarly, Lane and Milesi-Ferretti (2008) use a gravity framework—based on a multi-country extension of the Obstfeld and Rogoff (2000) model to explain international equity holdings. They find equity flows depend on the size of the source market, the economic size of the host country, and financial development levels. Aviat and Coeurdacier (2007) combine goods and asset trade in a unified gravity model and conclude that trade in goods is the primary channel through which distance affects asset holdings, with asset and goods flows mutually reinforcing.

Early empirical applications of gravity models to cross-border asset flows were a natural extension of trade gravity models, yet lacked rigorous theoretical foundations specific to financial markets. Okawa and van Wincoop (2012) (OvW) addressed this gap by deriving a structural gravity equation for asset trade within a static portfolio choice framework. They caution against ad hoc empirical approaches, such as the unwarranted inclusion of fixed effects or variables lacking theoretical justification, and demonstrate that, under certain conditions, asset trade can be governed by multilateral

¹⁶An Arrow-Debreu security pays one unit of a numeraire if a specific state materializes and zero otherwise.

resistance terms, as in trade.

Their model considers $N + 2$ assets: N country-specific risky assets (interpreted as equity, bonds, or bank claims), a risk-free asset with return R_f , and a global asset with return R_g that perfectly correlates with the global shock. This setup allows agents to hedge global risk, isolating country-specific risks as the relevant source of variation. The supply of asset by country i is denoted by K_i , representing country i 's capital stock.

The OvW structural asset trade gravity model builds on the core assumptions of traditional gravity models of trade, particularly those formalized by Anderson and van Wincoop (2003) (AvW). As in the trade context, the model assumes asset trade separability, bilateral frictions (such as distance or informational barriers), and general equilibrium conditions that give rise to multilateral resistance terms. These shared elements generate a gravity structure in which bilateral asset holdings depend positively on the economic size of the investor and issuer countries and negatively on transaction costs or frictions between them.

However, the asset trade gravity model incorporates important assumptions that are unique to financial markets. Unlike standard trade gravity models, such as AvW, which are typically derived from a framework with constant elasticity of substitution (CES) preferences over a continuum of goods, the OvW model is based on a mean-variance framework where investors are risk-averse and allocate their portfolios to maximize expected utility subject to return uncertainty. As a result, while trade models derive bilateral flows from consumption choices driven by relative prices and trade costs, asset flows in OvW respond to expected returns, variances, and covariances. This key difference underpins the derivation of the multilateral financial resistance term, which replaces the price-index-based multilateral resistance term used in CES-based trade models. Most notably, in OvW investors are assumed to be risk-averse and allocate their portfolios based on a mean-variance optimization framework, rather than utility from consumption. This introduces the role of return variances and covariances across countries, allowing for the modeling of global risk diversification. The model also features a multilateral financial resistance (MFR) term, which reflects the overall difficulty a country faces in accessing foreign assets, analogous to multilateral trade resistance but derived from financial frictions and risk-adjusted returns. Additionally, portfolio constraints such as home bias and limited diversification play a significant role in shaping cross-border asset holdings, distinguishing this framework from its trade counterpart.

Agents in country j choose consumption and portfolio allocations across all $N + 2$ assets. The portfolio share, α_{ij} , denotes the investment share of country j in the asset issued by country i , while α_{fj} and α_{gj} correspond to the allocations in the risk-free and the global asset, respectively. International financial frictions arise due to information asymmetries; domestic investors are better informed about local return components. For foreign agents, the variance of asset i 's innovation is $\tau_{ij}\sigma_i^2$ for $i \neq j$. This implies that σ_i^2 is the variance of the return (i.e., risk) of the country i 's asset for domestic investors. But for foreign investors from country j , the perceived or effective risk of

investing in asset i is higher and scaled by a factor $\tau_{ij} > 1$. This risk-based asymmetry is a central departure from gravity in goods trade. This introduces a risk-based asymmetry in cross-border asset demand as foreigners face higher effective volatility or uncertainty when holding foreign assets. This is a central departure from gravity models in goods trade, where the assumption is that prices and frictions are symmetric: a good exported from country i to j faces a trade cost, and that's it (risk perceptions are not part of the model in goods trade gravity). In contrast, in portfolio gravity models frictions include not just transaction costs, but also investor-specific risk perceptions. These asymmetric risk perceptions lead to home bias: investors prefer their own country's assets because they perceive them as safer.

The equity share α_{ij} depends on the ratio of the expected excess return to its variance. Okawa and van Wincoop (2012) define p_i as a risk-return ratio that plays a central role in their portfolio allocation model. The variable p_i is proportional to:

$$p_i \propto \frac{\sigma_i^2}{\mu_i - R_f}$$

where:

- σ_i^2 is the variance of the return on assets from country i (i.e., a measure of country-specific risk),
- μ_i is the expected return on assets from country i ,
- R_f is the risk-free rate (or the global return on the safe asset).

Specifically, it reflects how investors allocate their wealth across countries based on the trade-off between expected returns and risk, which adjusts in equilibrium to clear asset markets. It captures *the risk per unit of expected excess return* (i.e., the inverse of a Sharpe ratio). A higher p_i implies that the country i 's assets are relatively less attractive due to higher risk or lower expected returns, leading to lower demand for its assets in global portfolios. The bilateral investment share becomes:

$$\alpha_{ij} = \frac{1}{\tau_{ij} p_i}$$

Aggregating, total equity claims X_{ij} from j to i equal:

$$X_{ij} = \frac{P_j}{\tau_{ij} p_i} E_j \quad (1)$$

where $E_j = \sum_{i=1}^N \alpha_{ij} W_j$ is total equity investment by country j and P_j is a price index. Equation (1) reflects that asset demand depends on relative prices, specifically, p_i relative to P_j .

Combining individual demand and market-clearing conditions, they solve for p_i :

$$p_i = \frac{S}{S_i} \cdot \frac{1}{\Pi_i}, \quad \text{with} \quad \frac{1}{\Pi_i} = \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{P_j}{\tau_{ij}} \cdot \frac{E_j}{E}$$

Substituting yields to a gravity equation for financial assets, which is isomorphic to the typical one for structural trade gravity models¹⁷:

$$X_{ij} = \frac{S_i E_j}{E} \cdot \frac{\Pi_i P_j}{\tau_{ij}} \quad (2)$$

In the gravity equation for portfolio holdings, countries with a lower p_i (i.e., better risk-return trade-off) attract a larger share of global investment. This term helps explain the cross-country variation in portfolio allocations based not only on frictions (like distance or tax regimes) but also on fundamentals of asset performance. In analogy with goods trade, bilateral asset holdings depend on economic mass (size of source and destination) and relative frictions. However, in finance, frictions are driven by information and transaction costs, not transport.

The bilateral friction τ_{ij} is interpreted in relative terms, as $\tau_{ij}/(\Pi_i P_j)$, where Π_i and P_j are multilateral resistance terms that capture the average difficulty a country faces in global asset allocation.¹⁸ Higher Π_i implies that country i is relatively difficult to invest in globally; to clear its equity market, it must offer lower prices or higher returns, amplifying the effect of any given τ_{ij} on X_{ij} .

The key insight from Okawa and van Wincoop (2012) is that empirical gravity models of international asset allocation often fail to fully respect the structural constraints implied by the theory. A notable empirical regularity is the persistence of *home bias*, whereby investors disproportionately allocate funds to domestic assets. This bias is not solely rooted in investor preferences but also reflects institutional and regulatory barriers. Therefore, a theoretically consistent gravity model must incorporate not only market size and bilateral frictions but also multilateral resistance terms and institutional asymmetries. Expanding the set of explanatory variables to include political and regulatory dimensions significantly improves the model's empirical performance and alignment with observed global investment patterns.

Building upon this foundation, Pellegrino et al. (2022) proposed a novel theoretical framework inspired by Eaton and Kortum (2002). Their model integrates heterogeneous bilateral frictions into investor utility functions, allowing for preference heterogeneity across destination countries. Investors may favor certain foreign markets due to factors such as shared language, cultural proximity, or investment-related tax treaties. These bilateral factors are captured in a vector of frictions, where τ_{ij} denotes the effective tax burden borne by an investor from country j allocating capital to country i . Despite the novel modeling structure, the resulting empirical specification retains a gravity form, underlining the robustness of the gravity framework in capturing international asset allocation decisions.

In empirical work, gravity models are frequently combined with the push-pull framework to account for macroeconomic and financial factors. Brei and von Peter (2018) highlight the long-lasting

¹⁷Arkolakis et al. (2012) demonstrated that a large class of models generate isomorphic gravity equations despite having different underlying theoretical structures.

¹⁸As in Portes and Rey (2005) for equities and Buch (2005) for banking.

role of distance in cross-border banking, where information friction serves as an analog to transport costs. Galstyan and Lane (2013) demonstrate that initial bilateral positions, traditional gravity variables, and institutional linkages significantly shape portfolio adjustment dynamics. The latter factor is further emphasized by Binder et al. (2024), who stress the role of institutional infrastructure in capital reallocation. Other extensions of the gravity framework include the incorporation of asset quality differentiation, as proposed by Cavallaro and Cutrini (2019), who argue that investors discriminate between asset classes based on risk-return characteristics.

In the next Section, we present our empirical model. In the empirical literature, the most popular formula combines a gravity approach with the traditional analysis of pull-push factors, emphasizing information asymmetries. While there is some variation across studies, overall, the evidence suggests that gravitational variables such as economic size and distance play a significant role in explaining the patterns and determinants of cross-border asset trade flows together with bilateral frictions and multilateral resistance terms. Additionally, language barriers, regulatory variations, and institutional differences also exacerbate information asymmetry. These econometric specifications are sufficiently flexible to incorporate transaction costs. We use this model to formulate a testable equation for bilateral trade in equity and bonds, aligning with the relevant literature mentioned earlier.

4 Data, econometric methodology and empirical specification

4.1 Data

One common issue in the literature on tax havens is the challenge of gathering accurate and reliable data on cross-border investment flows. As noted earlier, financial intermediaries in tax havens may be subject to less stringent reporting standards, making it more difficult to track transactions.

Portfolio datasets typically follow either the residence or nationality principle to identify an investor's origin. The residence principle relies on physical location and is used in databases such as the IMF's CPIS¹⁹ and the dataset by Hobza and Zeugner (2014). Lane and Milesi-Ferretti (2018) provide a widely used dataset on countries' external positions that adjusts for valuation effects,²⁰ but it lacks bilateral detail, which limits its usefulness for our analysis. Additionally, although all these datasets offer consistent reporting, they fail to capture the role of tax havens, where financial intermediaries distort the link between the ultimate issuer and investor. To address this problem, Coppola et al. (2021) introduced a new database based on the nationality principle, linking securities issued in tax havens back to the home country of the parent company. In the same vein, recent efforts by the EU, particularly the ECB, have improved reporting standards and data transparency (Beck et al., 2024).

¹⁹The IMF CPIS has collected data since 1997. As of 2024, the IMF has introduced the Portfolio Investment Positions by Counterpart Economy dataset, which complements the existing CPIS and provides enhanced data granularity.

²⁰These include changes in asset prices and exchange rates, particularly relevant when positions are converted into a common currency

In this paper, we use the bilateral portfolio equity and bond database developed by Coppola et al. (2021), relying on their *issuance* methodology, which provides the broadest coverage of countries and issuer–investor relationships. Tax havens are classified following Hines (2010), which updates the earlier list from Hines and Rice (1994) and is widely used in the literature (Dharmapala et al., 2011; Desai et al., 2006). Following Torslov et al. (2023), the Netherlands is included due to its role as a major securities issuance center, while Switzerland is excluded. Table A3 presents the list of tax havens used in our study. Unlike Bricongne et al. (2023), we do not perform robustness checks across different lists (i.e. the multicriteria Oxfam list), as we exclusively rely on the classification embedded in the Coppola et al. (2021) database, which is comprehensive and broadly aligned with the IMF’s more restrictive list. Moreover, it includes the European OOFs most relevant for our purposes, such as Ireland, the Netherlands, and Luxembourg.²¹

The core insight of the Coppola et al. (2021) methodology is to remap securities issued in tax havens to the country of the ultimate parent. While traditional databases based on the residence principle associate securities with the intermediary’s location, this reclassification better reflects the true origin and destination of capital flows.²² Their database reassigns over 90% of securities issued by firms located in jurisdictions such as Bermuda, the Cayman Islands, Luxembourg, and others. For example, when a Swedish firm issues equity via an affiliate in Luxembourg purchased by a German investor, residence-based data records it as two transactions: issuance by Luxembourg and capital investment to Sweden. By contrast, the nationality-based database correctly links Sweden and Germany directly, eliminating artificial fragmentation. This is particularly relevant for measuring capital mobility and understanding global investment patterns (Coppola et al., 2021).

Table A1 presents EU investments in equity securities issued via tax havens. The CPIS data (residence-based) overstate the role of tax havens, whereas the nationality-based data from Coppola et al. (2021) re-map between 27% and 35% of equity holdings to the true issuer. Table A2 shows a similar pattern for U.S. investments in EU tax havens, with remapped shares peaking at 52% in 2015. These findings underscore the importance of properly accounting for tax havens in empirical analyses of cross-border portfolio allocation.

The Coppola et al. (2021) database covers bilateral equity and bond portfolio stocks between 2007 and 2017.²³ Our sample includes all observations involving at least one EU-28 country,²⁴ capturing EU investments in non-EU countries, non-EU investments in EU countries, and intra-EU portfolio allocation. When the EU acts as an investor, the Euro Area is treated as a consolidated block, due to fund centralization in OOFs.

The variables described below and in Table 2 have been chosen to specify a structural gravity model

²¹Delatte et al. (2022) show these countries host some of the highest levels of abnormal investment stocks.

²²However, it is worth noting that while the Coppola et al. (2021) database improves upon traditional sources, it is not free from criticism. A key assumption is that reallocation matrices based on Morningstar fund data are representative of all security investments, including those outside that dataset. The authors support this by showing that the restated positions align closely with those based on U.S. insurance holdings and Norway’s sovereign wealth fund.

²³See the complete country lists in Tables A4 and A5.

²⁴Including the UK, which was an EU member during the period.

for cross-country bilateral portfolio stocks following the theoretical model developed by Okawa and van Wincoop (2012). In particular, size, distance, and multilateral resistance are all included in the specification.

A key modeling choice in this article is the use of portfolio asset stocks, rather than flows, as the dependent variables for both equities and bonds. This choice is motivated by economic and econometric considerations. From an economic perspective, portfolio stocks reflect the accumulated impact of past investment decisions and thus capture long-term bilateral financial integration more accurately than short-term flows. From an econometric standpoint, stock data are typically less volatile and less sensitive to temporary shocks, facilitating more robust inference in cross-sectional and panel settings.

In this paper, we set a scenario in which several groups of variables explain the bilateral allocation of international portfolios in stock terms. Although in the traditional trade gravity literature the convention is to denote country i as the exporter (or sending country) and j as the importer (or receiving country), in this paper we follow the original notation introduced by Okawa and van Wincoop (2012) in their structural gravity model for international asset trade. In their framework, j refers to the investor country (the source of the portfolio outflow), while i denotes the destination country (where the asset is issued). We adopt this notation to maintain consistency with the theoretical model that underpins our analysis. To specify our empirical model we include, first, the main **gravity variables**, that is, *distance* between issuer and investor countries, as well as their respective *GDPs* to account for economic size, together with **additional gravitational variables** commonly used in the literature to account for historical links, such as *common official language*, and *colonial links*. Moreover, to be consistent with the gravity model by Okawa and van Wincoop (2012), we include in our benchmark model the resistance as **bilateral or multilateral barriers**. These resistances are introduced in two forms: First, the usual measures from trade gravity models based on bilateral distance and multilateral “remoteness” indexes²⁵, constructed as the logarithms GDP-weighted averages of bilateral distance (or trade costs).

$$\text{LnRI}(\text{IMP})_{it} = \ln \frac{\sum_j \text{DIST}_{ij}}{\frac{\text{GDP}_{jt}}{\text{WorldGDP}_t}} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{LnRI}(\text{EXP})_{jt} = \ln \frac{\sum_i \text{DIST}_{ij}}{\frac{\text{GDP}_{jt}}{\text{WorldGDP}_t}} \quad (4)$$

Second, we include in our specification two alternative measures of bilateral and multilateral resistance specially constructed for financial markets that we call *bilateral financial restrictions* or BFR faced by investor j when investing in issuer country i and *multilateral financial resistance* or MFR, defined as the relative position of bilateral barriers relative to average barriers with the rest of

²⁵We kept the same nomenclature (exporter and importer) as the trade literature, which correspond to investor and issuer, respectively, in the financial asset trade literature.

the world. In particular, bilateral financial resistance²⁶ is measured as financial restrictions in the investor and the issuer country, respectively. In contrast, MFR is the average global financial restrictions once the countries i and j have been excluded.

Finally, we include a set of additional controls to minimize omitted variable bias. Most importantly, we introduce a dummy for **European Union (EU) membership** to account for region-specific financial integration effects and the role of the European Central Bank (ECB). This variable is essential to capture the persistent *home bias* expected in EA portfolio allocations, particularly in bonds. As shown by De Santis and Gérard (2009), EA investors hold a disproportionately high share of domestic or intra-euro assets, despite formal capital mobility. Similarly, Lane (2006), Lane and Milesi-Ferretti (2008) and Coeurdacier and Martin (2009) document that monetary union significantly increased cross-border bond holdings within the EU, yet without fully eliminating home bias.

Second, we include a **global risk** variable, proxied by the VIX, to capture the influence of global financial conditions on portfolio flows. Uncertainty shocks are among the main drivers of extreme capital flow events such as sudden stops and retrenchments, with domestic fundamentals and capital controls playing a more limited role (Forbes and Warnock, 2012).²⁷

The complete list of variables and data sources is presented in Table 2.

4.2 Econometric methodology and model specification

Larch et al. (2025) provide a comprehensive review of best practices for estimating structural gravity models, advocating the use of panel data covering the cross-section and time dimension of datasets and the inclusion of fixed effects from time-varying origin and destination countries to serve as proxies for multilateral resistance terms (MRT). They also recommend incorporating country-pair fixed effects to address endogeneity in trade policies and to control for bilateral fixed trade costs, ensuring consistency between gravity fixed effects and structural terms. Moreover, they advise the inclusion of domestic flows in the dependent variable and the implementation of the Poisson Pseudo Maximum Likelihood (PPML) estimator to accommodate heteroskedasticity and zero-trade flows.

This paper estimates a gravity model of cross-border portfolio asset allocation (equity and bonds) using the PPML estimator developed by Santos Silva and Tenreyro (2006). Compared to the commonly used Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) on the log-linearized gravity model, PPML offers several advantages. OLS, while intuitive and straightforward to interpret, requires dropping zero flows, which is prevalent in financial datasets and leads to potential selection bias. Additionally, OLS

²⁶Bilateral financial restrictions between investor country j and issuer country i refer to the combined regulatory and institutional barriers that affect cross-border capital flows. These include: (a) outward investment restrictions in the investor country j , which must allow capital to be deployed abroad; and (b) inward investment restrictions in the issuer country i , which must permit foreign capital to be invested in domestic assets.

²⁷See also Binici et al. (2010); Nispi Landi and Schiavone (2021) for short-run capital control effects, and Boero et al. (2019); Bricongne et al. (2021) for more conditional findings.

assumes homoskedasticity, which is frequently violated in practice, resulting in inconsistent estimates.

By contrast, PPML handles zero observations naturally and is robust to heteroskedasticity, yielding consistent estimates even when the variance of the dependent variable varies across observations. This makes it especially suitable for unbalanced panels and datasets with a high incidence of zero positions, such as portfolio allocations between issuer and investor countries. The estimation is performed on the multiplicative form of the gravity equation, with two-way clustered standard errors.²⁸ To check for potential model misspecification, we conduct RESET tests for each specification.²⁹

While PPML is now the standard in gravity applications, it relies on the assumption that the conditional variance of the dependent variable is proportional to its conditional mean, i.e., a constant variance-to-mean ratio (CVMR) with $\lambda = 1$. However, overdispersion in financial data or complex specifications involving multilateral resistance terms can violate this assumption. To address this, Kwon et al. (2022), building on the iterated Generalized Method of Moments (iGMM) approach (Hansen and Lee, 2021), propose the Generalized PPML (G-PPML) estimator. G-PPML estimates the true value of λ directly from the data using iGMM and provides more efficient estimates when the CVMR assumption does not hold³⁰.

Following Bradley et al. (2023) and Kwon et al. (2022), we begin by comparing OLS and PPML estimators. Given the presence of zero flows and heteroskedasticity in our unbalanced panel, PPML clearly outperforms OLS and serves as the basis for our main results. As a robustness check, we also implement the G-PPML estimator using the routine by Kwon et al. (2022). While G-PPML yields efficiency gains when the CVMR assumption is rejected, standard PPML remains valid and performs well in most cases.

As for the econometric specification, we follow the guidelines proposed by Larch et al. (2025) as closely as possible. However, in certain cases—particularly regarding the treatment of high-dimensional fixed effects, we adapt their approach to suit the specificities of our empirical setting. In particular, we do not include country or country-pair fixed effects for two main reasons:

(a) First, our objective is to evaluate whether estimates that explicitly account for statistical distortions caused by tax havens improve the fit of a structural asset trade gravity model. To do so, it is essential to retain the estimates of standard gravity variables. Furthermore, we construct a model-specific multilateral resistance term and compare its performance to the conventional remoteness index. Including these covariates allows us to assess the relative contribution of gravity fundamentals, bilateral frictions, and multilateral resistance elements that would otherwise be absorbed by country or dyadic fixed effects.

²⁸Implemented using the `ppmlhdfc` command in Stata (Correia et al., 2020).

²⁹The null hypothesis of the RESET test is that the model is correctly specified. Rejection suggests omitted variables or functional form issues.

³⁰As noted by Kwon et al. (2022), point estimate differences may reach up to 40%.

(b) Second, we are constrained by the structure of the Coppola et al. (2021) database, where data are aggregated at the Euro Area level, largely due to the significant role played by OOFs within the EU. This aggregation precludes the use of country or country-pair fixed effects.

As Larch et al. (2025) recommend, when country-pair fixed effects cannot be included, time-invariant bilateral trade costs must be carefully modeled. Reflecting these considerations, our final specification excludes country and dyadic fixed effects but includes time-fixed effects to capture unobserved global shocks, such as trends in financial globalization, not otherwise accounted for by the gravity covariates. Additionally, we incorporate both time-invariant trade-cost proxies and time-varying gravity variables related to economic size and bilateral or multilateral frictions.

Accordingly, our empirical approach adopts a multiplicative gravity equation. This specification accounts for the structural features of the data while allowing us to identify the contribution of both time-invariant and time-varying gravity variables. Specifically, our estimation of the gravity model (2) relies on the following econometric form:

$$X_{ijt} = \exp[\gamma_1 W_{ij} + \gamma_2 Z_{ijt} + \lambda_t] \times \epsilon_{ijt} \quad (5)$$

where X_{ijt} stands for the portfolio stock from all possible investors (country j) to all possible issuers or destination countries i ³¹ included in Coppola et al. (2021) dataset. The data are in nominal terms and common currency. W_{ij} includes the gravity time-invariant control variables, such as distance, common language, and colonial links, γ_1 , and γ_2 are vectors of parameters and Z_{ijt} is a vector of time-varying gravity variables related to the elements mentioned previously in equation (2): the size or economic mass of the investor and the issuer country, bilateral and multilateral resistances as well as other additional variables also included in the model with a temporal dimension. Although to properly control for both observed and unobserved trade cost components, the inclusion of high-dimensional fixed effects has become standard practice in the gravity literature (Larch et al., 2025), in our case, however, and for the reasons outlined above, we include only time fixed effects (λ_t). While this approach is relatively less restrictive and may not fully capture all bilateral and multilateral resistance terms, raising concerns of potential omitted variable bias, it has the advantage of allowing the identification of traditional gravity covariates (such as the size of origin and destination countries, distance, etc.), which would otherwise be absorbed by more comprehensive sets of fixed effects. Lastly, $\epsilon_{j,it}$ is a white noise error with zero mean and constant variance that enters the specification as a multiplicative term.

We address the issue of potential omitted variables by carefully augmenting the model with additional covariates and applying the RESET test across different specifications to assess model adequacy. To mitigate concerns about reverse causality, particular attention is given to the construction of bilateral and multilateral financial resistance terms, combining both *de facto* and *de iure* financial

³¹We follow the original notation in Okawa and van Wincoop (2012). It is worth noting that this departs from the convention typically used in standard trade gravity models. The likely reason for this difference is that, in trade, the producer is also the exporter, whereas in financial markets, the issuer of assets corresponds to the destination country.

openness measures. Finally, to account for potential residual heteroskedasticity, we employ robust standard errors clustered at the country pair level.

We start our analysis with the most straightforward gravity equation, as presented in Equation (6) that we call **Baseline Model** in Tables 3 and 4 for equity and bonds, respectively. This specification includes distance, the two countries' GDP (size), colonial and language links, as well as the most usual measure of resistance: remoteness for the two countries. In the second half of the table, we propose an alternative baseline model, where remoteness is substituted by bilateral and multilateral resistance to asset trade (to measure financial restrictions or resistance), and that we show in equation (7).

Our baseline specification is derived from the theoretical model:

$$\text{Portf}_{ijt} = \exp[\beta_1 \ln(\text{dist}_{ij}) + \beta_2 \ln(\text{GDP}_{it}) + \beta_3 \ln(\text{GDP}_{jt}) + \beta_4 \text{comlang}_{ij} + \beta_5 \text{colony}_{ij} + \beta_6 \text{remote}_{it} + \beta_7 \text{remote}_{jt}] \times \varepsilon_{ijt} \quad (6)$$

Alternatively, we can substitute remoteness with bilateral and multilateral financial resistance:

$$\text{Portf}_{ijt} = \exp[\beta_1 \ln(\text{dist}_{ij}) + \beta_2 \ln(\text{GDP}_{it}) + \beta_3 \ln(\text{GDP}_{jt}) + \beta_4 \text{comlang}_{ij} + \beta_5 \text{colony}_{ij} + \beta_6 \text{BFR}_{it} + \beta_7 \text{BFR}_{jt} + \beta_8 \text{MFR}_{ijt}] \times \varepsilon_{ijt} \quad (7)$$

where "Portf" is the adopted portfolio definition (either equity or bonds), "dist" stands for distance, and "BFR" is the KOF index of economic globalization (defined in Table 1).³² In our empirical analysis, we use the mixed version of the KOF Globalization Index, as it offers the most comprehensive measure of financial integration. This choice is particularly appropriate for our purposes, as it captures both the realized intensity of cross-border financial interactions and the institutional and regulatory frameworks that shape them. The mixed index thus aligns well with the dual nature of financial integration, which depends not only on the observable flow of assets but also on the enabling policy environment.

It is important to bear in mind that bilateral asset trade between countries *i* and *j* depends not only on their individual characteristics and mutual financial frictions but also on the characteristics of all other countries and the barriers among them. In particular, any change in trade barriers affects all multilateral resistance terms (MRT), which in turn influences every bilateral trade flow. These general equilibrium effects are distinct from the direct impact of changes in bilateral financial barriers (τ_{ij}) on trade. From a theoretical standpoint, MRTs are among the most critical components

³²To proxy for financial integration, we rely on the KOF Globalization Index, developed by the KOF Swiss Economic Institute. The index provides three distinct measures of globalization: the *de facto* version, which captures actual flows and activities such as trade, capital movements, and information exchange; the *de iure* version, which reflects policy and institutional arrangements like trade regulations, investment restrictions, and international treaties; and a third, *mixed* version that combines both dimensions.

in the model, as they capture the general equilibrium adjustments implied by the structural framework (Gervais, 2025). These terms are not observable in the data and must be estimated—either through fixed effects or suitable proxies. In our case, we propose a novel proxy, the Multilateral Financial Resistance (MFR), to reflect the financial analog of MRT. As an alternative, we also employ the standard remoteness index, widely used in trade gravity models and defined in Bradley et al. (2023). Except for the inclusion of historical link variables (such as common language and colonial ties), our baseline specification follows the structural gravity approach of Okawa and van Wincoop (2012).

We conduct several robustness checks on the baseline model to ensure the reliability of our findings:

First, as shown in Table 5, we compare the estimation results of the baseline specification using PPML and its generalized version, G-PPML, to assess the sensitivity of our results to the choice of estimator.

Second, in Table 6 for equity and bonds, respectively—we incrementally extend the baseline gravity model by including additional explanatory variables. First, we introduce a dummy variable (*EU pair*) equal to 1 when both countries are EU members, to capture potential home bias within the Union. Next, we include a global risk variable (VIX, the CBOE Volatility Index) to account for the possibility that agents hedge against global uncertainty through asset diversification. Given that a higher global risk typically reduces capital mobility, this variable helps isolate any remaining effects of global uncertainty.

Third, and finally, as shown in Tables 7 and 8, we address potential concerns related to data construction. To validate the robustness of our results and highlight the advantages of the Coppola et al. (2021) dataset, we replicate our estimations using portfolio positions from the IMF’s CPIS dataset.

According to the theory, portfolio choices are expected to be negatively affected by distance, as remote countries tend to invest less in each other. However, economic size is expected to positively affect portfolio holding allocation. The literature on gravity also suggests a positive effect on historical links. For the case of the resistance variables, two opposite effects are at play; first, we should expect a negative impact from bilateral resistance since this implies an increase of financial restrictions between the two countries; concerning the financial restrictions from the rest of the world, an increase would have a positive effect, given that more restrictions in the rest of the world relative to the investor and issuer countries would make it more difficult for both countries to trade with the rest of the world than between them. The risk variable is expected to hurt portfolio holdings invested in each other, given the negative role that risk/uncertainty plays on capital mobility. Finally, EU pair dummy is expected to be positive due to the home bias observed in section 2.

5 Results

5.1 Portfolio equity estimations

In this section, we discuss the results³³ presented in Table 3. Our baseline specification closely follows benchmark theoretical models and employs the database constructed by Coppola et al. (2021) under the nationality principle. The first four columns include the remoteness index in the specification, while the remaining four columns utilize our proposed measures of bilateral and multilateral financial friction. These correspond, *de facto*, to the econometric specifications derived from Anderson and van Wincoop (2003) (AvW) and Okawa and van Wincoop (2012) (OvW), respectively. In both cases, we compare estimation results using OLS and PPML, with and without time-fixed effects.

We begin with OLS without fixed effects and then introduce fixed effects before transitioning to PPML estimations. The gravity variables are both correctly signed and significant using the OLS and the PPML estimators. However, the PPML estimator clearly outperforms OLS in terms of model fit and robustness. The sample in the OLS estimations is significantly reduced due to the exclusion of zero observations, and the OLS estimation yields lower R^2 values and shows signs of misspecification according to the RESET test. Therefore, the specifications estimated through PPML emerge as the preferred models. The results are reported in Table 3. Overall, the estimates are in line with the large empirical literature on the gravity equation. In particular, distance is negatively associated with cross-border equity investment, consistent with models where distance correlates with information asymmetries and transaction costs. The GDP of both investor and issuer countries enters positively and significantly with elasticities greater than one, meaning that GDP size is positively correlated with mutual equity investment activity. Additionally, historical ties, such as common language, also show a strong and positive correlation (both with and without time-fixed effects), as the estimated language coefficients are all positive and three out of four are statistically significant at the one percent level. Finally, with one exception, the colonial indicators are not statistically significant at conventional levels and do not all have the same sign. As indicated at the bottom of Table 3, the R^2 values are all very high, ranging from about 0.91 to 0.95. This suggests that the theoretical models explain a large fraction of the variance in equity trade.

Interestingly, trade resistance variables, such as bilateral remoteness, are only significant at 10% levels in the PPML models in some cases. The results improve when we use our measure of financial resistance. The best model is the one estimated by PPML with fixed-time effects (last column of Table 3). Not only the bilateral financial resistance, BFR_{it} and BFR_{jt} but also the multilateral financial resistance, MFR_{ij} , are highly significant and have the correct signs: negative for the individual countries and positive for multilateral resistance, as expected. Finally, this model passes the RESET misspecification test.

³³The coefficients of logged regressors (distance and GDPs) represent elasticities and can therefore be interpreted directly. However, coefficients of non-logged regressors (i.e., all other variables) represent semi-elasticities. For correct interpretation, they should be transformed using the formula $(e^\beta - 1) \times 100$.

These findings also raise questions about the suitability of the remoteness index as a measure of trade resistance in the context of equity assets. Unlike goods trade, financial transactions do not incur physical transport costs. Hence, the concept of geographic isolation may not capture meaningful frictions in financial markets for global assets. In fact, informational asymmetries are already proxied by the distance variable. Financial restrictions give a more appropriate measure of resistance in financial integration, both *de iure* and *de facto*, which directly constrain cross-border asset holdings. These are better captured through the construction of bilateral and multilateral financial resistance terms, which we include and analyze in subsequent specifications.

5.2 Portfolio bond estimations

Table 4 reports the gravity model estimations for bond holdings, following the same structure as the equity specifications. We estimate OLS models first, without and then with fixed effects, and then shift to PPML estimations. As in the case of equities, the PPML estimator clearly outperforms OLS. The OLS sample is significantly reduced due to the exclusion of zeros, shows lower R^2 values, and exhibits signs of model misspecification (as none of the specifications pass the RESET test, as was also the case with equity). Moreover, the estimated coefficients on the gravity variables under OLS are less precise and often lose statistical significance.

In contrast, the PPML model provides a more robust estimation. Distance enters the regression with a negative and statistically significant coefficient, consistent with the interpretation of distance as a proxy for information asymmetries in financial markets. Both the GDP of the investor and the issuer countries display significant and positive coefficients larger than one, confirming that larger economies tend to invest more heavily in each other's bond markets. Gravity variables capturing historical ties, such as common language and colonial links, are also positive and significant, reinforcing the role of historical relationships in shaping cross-border asset allocation.

An important distinction concerning equity holdings emerges when examining the coefficients on the remoteness indexes. In the case of bonds, these variables are positive and significant, suggesting that bond trading is positively associated with geographic proximity and relative isolation from global financial systems. This result can be interpreted as evidence that bonds are less internationally mobile than equities and are subject to a regional investment bias.

A comparative analysis of the results for equity and bond holdings yields several insights. First, distance appears to be a more relevant factor for bonds than for equities. This is consistent with portfolio debt investments being more geographically concentrated, showing stronger correlations with proximity to neighboring countries. In addition, we find that multilateral resistance terms are less influential in the case of bonds. This pattern coincides with strong intra-European Union investment concentrations and weaker associations with financial frictions involving third countries. As a result, financial restrictions outside the EU show weaker correlations with bond investment patterns.

Second, comparing the two models of resistance, remoteness index versus financial restriction resistance, reveals notably higher explanatory power in the latter. In fact, when resistance is modeled through financial restrictions, the estimated coefficients exhibit the expected signs and statistical significance.³⁴

From a theoretical standpoint, this divergence is consistent with the unique nature of financial asset trade compared to goods trade. Unlike goods, financial assets are not subject to physical transport costs, so geographic isolation does not necessarily impede trade. Instead, cross-border asset allocation patterns are most strongly correlated with financial regulations and restrictions. Thus, bilateral and multilateral financial resistance measures, which reflect both barriers, *de iure* and *de facto*, provide a more appropriate framework to capture the true constraints on financial integration.

5.3 Robustness checks

As robustness checks, we conduct three complementary exercises. First, we compare alternative estimators, PPML and GPPML, to assess the sensitivity of our results to the estimation method. Second, we extend the baseline model to explicitly test for home bias and the role of global risk factors. Third, we replicate the baseline model using two different datasets to evaluate the consistency of our findings across data sources and assess the distortionary effects of tax havens.

In Table 5, to assess the robustness of our baseline estimates, we reestimate the gravity model using the GPPML estimator. In the case of the financial restriction resistance specification, the estimated dispersion parameter λ is not statistically different from one. This confirms that the standard PPML estimator remains the most efficient choice for this model, which is in line with theoretical expectations. Conversely, when the remoteness index is used as the multilateral resistance proxy, λ differs significantly from one, suggesting that the GPPML estimator offers efficiency gains in this setting. However, despite these differences in the optimal estimation technique, the main findings remain consistent across specifications. The estimated coefficients retain similar magnitudes and significance levels under both PPML and GPPML. Therefore, our earlier conclusions regarding the impact of gravity variables and financial frictions on cross-border asset holdings continue to hold.

To remain close to the parsimonious structure of the OvW model, we extend our baseline gravity specification by including only two additional covariates designed to test key theoretical predictions: home bias and the irrelevance of global risk, which can be hedged through portfolio diversification. Specifically, we add an EU membership dummy and a global risk factor. The estimation results are presented in Table 6. Columns 1 and 2 report results for equity (without and with fixed effects), while Columns 3 and 4 present the corresponding estimates for bonds. The EU dummy is positive and statistically significant for portfolio bonds, indicating a strong intra-EU bias. This suggests

³⁴The only exception is the bond model estimated with PPML and fixed effects. However, according to the RESET test, the PPML model without fixed effects can also be interpreted as valid.

that bond allocations within the EU are disproportionately high, likely reflecting institutional harmonization and reduced transaction costs—consistent with the stylized facts discussed in Section 2. The inclusion of the EU dummy also reduces the magnitude of the distance coefficient, as EU countries tend to be geographically closer, and part of the spatial variation is absorbed.

Notably, when the EU dummy is included, the MFR term becomes statistically significant and correctly signed in the bond regressions. This contrasts with the baseline specification, where MFR was not significant for bonds, and supports our earlier hypothesis that its lack of explanatory power was driven by unobserved intra-EU factors now captured by the EU dummy.

Regarding the global risk variable, we find a negative coefficient for both asset classes, though it is statistically significant only for equity—consistent with the view that equity flows are more sensitive to global uncertainty due to their higher volatility and risk-return profile. However, this variable is included only in the specification without time-fixed effects, as the inclusion of time-fixed effects absorbs all common global shocks, such as trends in financial globalization or shifts in global risk sentiment, making it redundant in those regressions.

Finally, we replicate our baseline estimations using an alternative dataset: the Coordinated Portfolio Investment Survey (CPIS) from the IMF, which follows the residence principle. This contrasts with our primary dataset, which is based on the nationality principle and adjusts for holdings channeled through tax havens. Tables 7 and 8 present the results for equity and bond holdings, respectively. Again, we estimate the AvW and OvW models using OLS and PPML with and without time-fixed effects, with the PPML estimator being the best one, according to other indicators, such as the RESET test. When using CPIS data, we find that gravity variables such as distance and economic size remain significant, though their coefficients are attenuated. Historical ties also retain their expected positive effect, particularly for bonds, reflecting persistent long-term investment patterns. The remoteness index becomes significant under the residence principle, indicating stronger bilateral asset holdings among geographically isolated countries, unlike in the nationality-based data, where equity appears more globally mobile. This pattern contrasts with our findings under the nationality principle, where portfolio equity is shown to be more globally mobile. Moreover, when we look at the financial resistance, the multilateral financial resistance variable displays an unexpected negative sign, which is against the theoretical OvW model, undermining its reliability in this framework. These results imply that using data based on the residence principle, without adjusting for the role of offshore financial centers, can obscure the true effects of both gravitational and general equilibrium factors. In particular, the presence of tax havens appears to blur the true origin of portfolio asset allocation across borders, so that the multilateral financial resistance variable is poorly estimated and displays the wrong sign, casting doubt on its validity. Finally, R^2 shows lower values using the residence principle to assign the investor country (0.65-0.68 vs. 0.95). Overall, these robustness checks confirm that failing to adjust for the role of tax havens can distort the estimated influence of gravity and resistance variables. This leads to an underestimation of the true degree of international portfolio mobility, both for equity and bond investments.

In conclusion, the gravity models estimated for equity and bonds portfolio holdings differ depending on the principle (residence or nationality) applied to obtain the data. When the nationality principle is used, the results are more coherent with the theoretical model. Therefore, correctly remapping portfolio holdings channeled through tax havens is crucial.

6 Summary and conclusions

Following a gravity approach, this research examines the factors associated with cross-border portfolio allocation involving any EU countries with the rest of the world from 2007 to 2017. The salient feature of our approach is accounting for the distortionary role of tax havens by using the recent database by Coppola et al. (2021), which remaps portfolio stocks to ultimate partners (nationality principle), in contrast to traditional databases built under the residence principle, such as the IMF-CPIS. We estimate the gravity equation based on the model proposed by Okawa and van Wincoop (2012), in which bilateral and multilateral resistances to asset trade are modeled as financial restrictions. Our results show that this empirical specification is more informative than the one derived from a structural trade gravity model (AvW) using remoteness as proxy for multilateral resistance. Using PPML, we estimate a baseline specification including distance, size, historical links, and bilateral and multilateral resistances. We then extend our baseline model to capture the potential roles of an EU dummy variable (as a proxy for border or home bias effects, particularly for bonds) and global risk on portfolio holdings. For comparability, we repeat our analysis using the IMF-CPIS database to assess differences when tax haven presence is not accounted for.

Our results yield three main findings. First, gravitational variables are significant with expected signs: distance is negatively associated with holdings, while economic mass is positively correlated with investment, as large countries tend to invest more between themselves. Bilateral resistance is negatively associated with equity holdings, consistent with financial restrictions being correlated with lower cross-border investments, while multilateral financial restrictions exhibit a positive sign, meaning that financial restrictions elsewhere are positively correlated with bilateral asset trade. Second, global risk shows only a weak significant association in the case of equity, consistent with effective hedging as predicted by the OvW model. Additional gravity variables show expected signs and significance: historical links and the EU dummy are positive, with the latter significant only for bonds, providing evidence of home bias effects (consistent with the stylized facts in Section 2).

Portfolio equity and bonds exhibit distinct characteristics, reflecting their different risk profiles. Distance and the EU dummy show stronger associations with bonds, consistent with portfolio bonds being more concentrated among neighboring issuers, due to the ECB's role as bond purchaser in open market operations. Consequently, EU debt tends to remain within the EU, particularly in euro-area countries. In contrast, portfolio equity demonstrates greater international mobility and higher sensitivity to financial restrictions elsewhere and global risk. Despite these differences, both assets show similar associations with historical links. These results are robust to different estimation methods.

Repeating our analysis using the IMF-CPIS database reveals substantial differences in gravity variables for both portfolio equity and bonds. Distance becomes less relevant under the residence principle, as does economic size. While bilateral financial restrictions yield similar results across databases, multilateral resistance shows much more limited effects under the residence principle, even turning negative, the opposite to the predictions of the OvW model. Moreover, the explanatory power of the estimated model is considerably lower when using the IMF-CPIS database. These differences underscore the importance of addressing the distortionary effects of tax havens, as ignoring them obscures the empirical results.

References

- Anderson, J. E. and van Wincoop, E. (2003). Gravity with Gravitas : A Solution to the Border Puzzie. *The American Economic Review*, 93(1):170–192.
- Arkolakis, C., Costinot, A., and Rodríguez-Clare, A. (2012). New Trade Models, Same Old Gains? *American Economic Review*, 102(1):94–130.
- Avdjiev, S., Subelyte, A., and Takats, E. (2016). The ECB’s QE and euro cross-border bank lending. *BIS Quarterly Review*, 16(September):99–113.
- Aviat, A. and Coeurdacier, N. (2007). The geography of trade in goods and asset holdings. *Journal of International Economics*, 71(1):22–51.
- Baele, L., Ferrando, A., Hördahl, P., and Monnet, C. (2004). Measuring Financial Integration in the Euro Area. *ECB Occasional Paper Series*, 14.
- Beck, R., Coppola, A., Lewis, A., Maggiori, M., Schmitz, M., and Schreger, J. (2024). The Geography of Capital Allocation in the Euro Area. *NBER Working Paper Series*, 32275.
- Bertaut, C. C., Bressler, B., and Curcuru, S. (2019). Globalization and the Geography of Capital Flows. *FEDS Notes*, 2019(2446):30–31.
- Binder, M., Cheung, Y. L., Georgiadis, G., and Sharma, S. (2024). Institutions, international financial integration, and output. *Journal of Economic Behavior and Organization*, 219(August 2023):450–472.
- Binici, M., Hutchison, M., and Schindler, M. (2010). Controlling capital? Legal restrictions and the asset composition of international financial flows. *Journal of International Money and Finance*, 29(4):666–684.
- Black, S. and Munro, S. (2010). Why issue bonds offshore? *Bank for International Settlements*, 334:1–55.
- Boero, G., Mandalinci, Z., and Taylor, M. P. (2019). Modelling portfolio capital flows in a global framework: Multilateral implications of capital controls. *Journal of International Money and Finance*, 90:142–160.
- Bradley, S., Carril-Caccia, F., and Yotov, Y. (2023). Reassessing the Effects of Corporate Income Taxes on Mergers and Acquisitions Using Empirical Advances in the Gravity Literature. *CESifo Working Paper*, 23(10863).
- Brei, M. and von Peter, G. (2018). The distance effect in banking and trade. *Journal of International Money and Finance*, 81:116–137.

- Bricongne, J.-C., Cosson, A., Garnier-Sauveplane, A., Lecat, R., Peresa, I., and Vanzhulova, Y. (2021). Financial flows, macro-prudential policies, capital restrictions and institutions: what do gravity equations tell us? *Banque de France Working Paper*, 2021(842).
- Bricongne, J.-C., Delpuech, S., and Lopez-Forero, M. (2023). Productivity slowdown and tax havens: Where is measured value creation? *Journal of International Economics*, 143:103757.
- Buch, C. M. (2005). Distance and international banking. *Review of International Economics*, 13(4):787–804.
- Caballero, R. J., Farhi, E., and Gourinchas, P. O. (2008). An equilibrium model of global imbalances and low interest rates. *American Economic Review*, 98(1):358–393.
- Calvo, G. A., Leiderman, L., and Reinhart, C. M. (1993). Capital Inflows and Real Exchange Rate Appreciation in Latin America. *Staff Papers (International Monetary Fund)*, 40(1):108–151.
- Calvo, G. A., Leiderman, L., and Reinhart, C. M. (1996). Inflows of capital to developing countries in the 1990s. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 10(2):217–223.
- Cassetta, A., Pauselli, C., Rizzica, L., and Tonello, M. (2014). Questioni di economia e finanza (Occasional papers). *Questioni di Economia e Finanza. 14Banca d'Italia*, 14(4).
- Cavallaro, E. and Cutrini, E. (2019). Distance and beyond: What drives financial flows to emerging economies? *Economic Modelling*, 81(November 2017):533–550.
- Coeurdacier, N. and Martin, P. (2009). The geography of asset trade and the euro: Insiders and outsiders. *Journal of the Japanese and International Economies*, 23(2):90–113.
- Coppola, A., Maggiori, M., Neiman, B., and Schreger, J. (2021). Redrawing the Map of Global Capital Flows: The Role of Cross-Border Financing and Tax Havens. *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 136(3):1499–1556.
- Correia, S., Guimarães, P., and Zylkin, T. Z. (2020). Fast Poisson estimation with high-dimensional fixed effects. *Stata Journal*, 20(1):95–115.
- Damgaard, J., Elkjaer, T., and Johannesen, N. (2019). What Is Real and What Is Not in the Global FDI Network? *IMF Working Papers*, 19(274).
- De Santis, R. A. and Gérard, B. (2009). International portfolio reallocation: Diversification benefits and European monetary union. *European Economic Review*, 53(8):1010–1027.
- Delatte, A.-L., Guillin, A., and Vicard, V. (2022). Grey zones in global finance: The distorted geography of cross-border investments. *Journal of International Money and Finance*, 120:102540.
- Desai, M. A., Foley, C. F., and Hines, J. R. (2006). The demand for tax haven operations. *Journal of Public Economics*, 90(3):513–531.
- Dharmapala, D. (2008). What problems and opportunities are created by tax havens. *Oxford Review of Economic Policy*, 24(4):661–679.
- Dharmapala, D., Foley, C. F., and Forbes, K. J. (2011). Watch What I Do, Not What I Say: The Unintended Consequences of the Homeland Investment Act. *Journal of Finance*, 66(3):753–787.

- Dharmapala, D. and Hines, J. R. (2009). Which countries become tax havens? *Journal of Public Economics*, 93(9-10):1058–1068.
- Eaton, J. and Kortum, S. (2002). Technology, Geography, and Trade. *Econometrica*, 70(5):1741–1779.
- ECB Committee on Financial Integration (2022). Financial Integration and Structure in the Euro Area. Technical Report 22, ECB, Frankfurt, April.
- Fernandez-Arias, E. (1996). The new wave of private capital inflows: Push or pull? *Journal of Development Economics*, 48(2):389–418.
- Fonseca, L., Nikalixi, K., and Papaioannou, E. (2023). The globalization of corporate control. *Journal of International Economics*, 146:103754.
- Forbes, K. J. and Warnock, F. E. (2012). Capital flow waves: Surges, stops, flight, and retrenchment. *Journal of International Economics*, 88(2):235–251.
- Galstyan, V. and Lane, P. R. (2013). Bilateral portfolio dynamics during the global financial crisis. *European Economic Review*, 57:63–74.
- Gervais, A. (2025). A decomposition of the variance of international trade flows. *Empirical Economics*, 68(5):2073–2092.
- Gullo, V. and Montalbano, P. (2022). Financial transparency and anomalous portfolio investment flows: A gravity analysis. *Journal of International Money and Finance*, 128:102704.
- Hansen, B. E. and Lee, S. (2021). Inference for Iterated GMM Under Misspecification. *Econometrica*, 89(3):1419–1447.
- Hau, H. and Rey, H. (2006). Exchange rates, equity prices, and capital flows. *Review of Financial Studies*, 19(1):273–317.
- Hines, J. R. (2010). Treasure islands. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 24(4):103–126.
- Hines, J. R. and Rice, E. M. (1994). Fiscal Paradise: Foreign Tax Havens and American Business. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 109(1):149–182.
- Hobza, A. and Zeugner, S. (2014). Current accounts and financial flows in the euro area. *Journal of International Money and Finance*, 48(PB):291–313.
- IMF (2000). Offshore Financial Centers. *IMF Background Paper*.
- IMF (2009). *Balance of Payments and International Investment Positions*, volume 1. IMF, Washington DC, 6th edition.
- Koepke, R. (2019). What Drives Capital Flows To Emerging Markets? a Survey of the Empirical Literature. *Journal of Economic Surveys*, 33(2):516–540.
- Koepke, R. and Paetzold, S. (2020). Capital Flow Data. A Guide for Empirical Analysis and Real-Time Tracking. *IMF Working Paper*, 171.
- Kwon, O., Syropoulos, C., and Yotov, Y. (2022). Do Sanctions Affect Growth? *CESifo Working Papers*, 22(June).

- Lane, P. R. (2006). Global Bond Portfolios and EMU. *International Journal of Central Banking*, 2:1–23.
- Lane, P. R. and Milesi-Ferretti, G. M. (2008). International investment patterns. *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 90(3):538–549.
- Lane, P. R. and Milesi-Ferretti, G. M. (2011). Cross-border investment in small international financial centres. *International Finance*, 14(2):301–330.
- Lane, P. R. and Milesi-Ferretti, G. M. (2018). The External Wealth of Nations Revisited: International Financial Integration in the Aftermath of the Global Financial Crisis. *IMF Economic Review*, 66(1):189–222.
- Larch, M., Shikher, S., and Yotov, Y. V. (2025). Estimating Gravity Equations : Theory Implications , Econometric Developments , and Practical Recommendations. *CGPA Working Paper*, 25(1).
- Lopez, G. G. and Stracca, L. (2021). Changing patterns of capital flows: Committee on the Global Financial System. *CGFS Papers*, 21(66):1–98.
- Martin, P. and Rey, H. (2004). Financial super-markets: Size matters for asset trade. *Journal of International Economics*, 64(2):335–361.
- Mendoza, E. G., Quadrini, V., and Ríos-Rull, J. V. (2009). Financial integration, financial development, and global imbalances. *Journal of Political Economy*, 117(3):371–416.
- Milesi-Ferretti, G.-M., Tamirisa, N. T., and Stobbe, F. (2010). Bilateral Financial Linkages and Global Imbalances: A View on the Eve of the Financial Crisis. *IMF Working Papers*, 10(257):1.
- Nispi Landi, V. and Schiavone, A. (2021). The Effectiveness of Capital Controls. *Open Economies Review*, 32(1):183–211.
- Obstfeld, M. and Rogoff, K. (2000). The Six Major Puzzles in International Macroeconomics: Is There a Common Cause? *NBER Macroeconomics Annual 2000*, 15:339–390.
- Okawa, Y. and van Wincoop, E. (2012). Gravity in International Finance. *Journal of International Economics*, 87(2):205–215.
- Pellegrino, B., Spolaore, E., and Wacziarg, R. (2022). Barriers to Global Capital Allocation. *NBER Working Paper Series*, 2.
- Portes, R. and Rey, H. (1998). The Euro and International Equity Flows. *Journal of the Japanese and International Economies*, 12(4):406–423.
- Portes, R. and Rey, H. (2005). The determinants of cross-border equity flows. *Journal of International Economics*, 65(2):269–296.
- Rose, A. K. and Spiegel, M. M. (2007). Offshore financial centres: Parasites or symbionts? *Economic Journal*, 117(523):1310–1335.
- Santacreu, A. M. (2023). International Technology Licensing, Intellectual Property Rights, and Tax Havens. *Review of Economics and Statistics*, pages 1–45.
- Santos Silva, J. and Tenreyro, S. (2006). The log of gravity. *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 88(November):641–658.

Sarno, L., Tsiakas, I., and Ulloa, B. (2016). What drives international portfolio flows? *Journal of International Money and Finance*, 60:53–72.

Torslov, T., Wier, L., and Zucman, G. (2023). The Missing Profits of Nations. *The Review of Economic Studies*, 90(3):1499–1534.

UNCTAD (2024). World investment report. Investment facilitation and digital government. Technical report, United Nations, New York, NY, USA.

Figures

Figure 1: World tax havens

Notes: (a) Data obtained from the IMF (CPIS) database (residence principle); (b) Tax havens included in the graph are listed in table A3.

Figure 2: Total EU tax havens in %

Notes: (a) Data obtained from the IMF (CPIS) database (residence principle); (b) EU tax havens: Cyprus, Ireland, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands.

Figure 3: EU portfolio equity investment position by issuer country

Notes: (a) The nationality principle position (left chart) comes from Coppola et al. (2021); (b) The residence principle (right chart) position has been obtained from the IMF (CPIS) database; (c) Croatia is only included in the Coppola et al. (2021) database on the investor but not on the issuer side. (d) CYM= Cayman Islands, DEU = Germany, FR = FRANCE, GBR = United Kingdom, IRL = Ireland, ITA = Italy, JPN = Japan, LUX = Luxembourg, NLD = The Netherlands, USA = United States. (f) CYM has been rounded up to 3% to fit into the pie chart (actual = 2,2%).

Figure 4: EU portfolio bond investment position by issuer country

Notes: (a) The nationality principle position (left chart) comes from Coppola et al. (2021); (b) The residence principle (right chart) position has been obtained from the IMF (CPIS) database; (c) Croatia is only included in the Coppola et al. (2021) database on the investor but not on the issuer side; (d) DEU = Germany, ESP = Spain, FR = FRANCE, GBR = United Kingdom, IRL = Ireland, ITA = Italy, LUX = Luxembourg, NLD = The Netherlands, USA = United States.

Tables

Table 1: EU portfolio equity investment position

Investor	Issuer EU - Investor EU	Issuer Euro Area - Investor EU
Euro Area members	61%	84%
Non-members of Euro area		
Bulgaria	71%	93%
Czech Republic	82%	92%
Denmark	40%	64%
Hungary	78%	86%
Poland	64%	89%
Romania	95%	94%
Sweden	47%	76%
United Kingdom	26%	91%

Notes: (a) Data obtained from Coppola et al. (2021), under the nationality principle; (b) Croatia is only included in the Coppola et al. (2021) database on the investor but not on the issuer side. (b) Data covers the full sample period (2007-2017).

Table 2: List of variables

Variables	Definition	Source
Dependent variable		
Portfolio equity stock	Portfolio equity stock between investor and issuer countries.	Coppola et al. (2021)
Portfolio bond stock	Portfolio bond stock between investor and issuer countries.	Coppola et al. (2021)
Gravity variables		
Distance	Distance between the most populated cities of each country in km.	CEPII
Economic size	EMU (investor) values are the average of individual EMU countries.	World bank open data
Common language	Investor and issuer's GDP (constant 2015 USD). Millions.	CEPII
Colony	Takes value of 1 when both share common official or primary language.	CEPII
Financial resistance		
Bilateral financial resistance investor (BFR_i)	Economic Globalization index combined de iure and de facto measure (KOFecGI) of the investor country.	Gygli et al. (2019) and Dreher (2006)
	The index ranges between 1 (lowest openness level) and 100 (highest openness level) Economic frictions are the difference between frictionless economic openness (100) minus the actual country value.	
	EMU values are the GDP-weighted average of individual EMU countries.	
Bilateral financial resistance issuer (BFR_i)	Economic Globalization index combined de iure and de facto measure (KOFecGI) of the issuer country.	Gygli et al. (2019) and Dreher (2006)
	The index ranges between 1 (lowest openness level) and 100 (highest openness level) Economic frictions are the difference between frictionless economic openness (100) minus the actual country value.	
	EMU values are the GDP-weighted average of individual EMU countries.	
Multilateral financial resistance (MFR_{ij})	Also based on KOFecGI as above. Ranges between 1 and 100.	Gygli et al. (2019) and Dreher (2006)
	For the multilateral measure, we use the world average, excluding investor and issuer countries. EMU values are the GDP-weighted average of individual EMU countries.	

Notes: CEPII=Centre d'Etudes Prospectives et d'Informations Internationales, IMF=International Monetary Fund, WGI=Worldwide Governance Indicators.

Table 2: List of variables. Cont.

Variables	Definition	Source
Remoteness index		
Remoteness index exporter ($RI(EXP)_j$)	Logarithm of the weighted averaged of importer's GDP over world's GDP of bilateral distance.	Own calculations
Remoteness index importer ($RI(IMP)_i$)	Logarithm of the weighted averaged of exporter's GDP over world's GDP of bilateral distance.	
Additional variables		
European Union membership	Takes value of 1 when both investor and issuer are EU members.	Own calculations
Global uncertainty/risk	CBOE Volatility Index (VIX).	FRED database

Notes: CEPII=Centre d'Etudes Prospectives et d'Informations Internationales, IMF=International Monetary Fund, WGI=Worldwide Governance Indicators.

Table 3: Baseline model. Portfolio equity data. Nationality principle.

	Remoteness index				Financial resistance			
	OLS	OLS FE	PPML	PPML FE	OLS	OLS FE	PPML	PPML FE
Gravity								
$\ln(\text{Dist})_{ij}$	-0.23*	-0.23***	-0.57***	-0.57***	-0.04	-0.01	-0.14	-0.22***
$\ln(\text{GDP})_j$	0.81***	0.81***	0.95***	0.94***	0.91***	0.95***	0.98***	1.24***
$\ln(\text{GDP})_i$	0.94***	0.94***	1.19***	1.18***	1.03***	1.01***	1.16***	1.18***
Other gravity								
Common language _{<i>j</i>}	0.72**	0.72**	1.12***	1.12***	1.05***	1.14***	0.49**	0.64***
Colony _{<i>ij</i>}	0.54*	0.54*	-0.33	-0.32	0.17	0.35	-0.12	-0.34*
Remoteness index								
$RI(\text{EXP})_j$	0.05	0.05	-0.06*	-0.06*	-	-	-	-
$RI(\text{IMP})_i$	0.13**	0.13**	0.08	0.08	-	-	-	-
Bilateral financial resistance								
BFR (investor) _{<i>j</i>}	-	-	-	-	-0.10***	-0.09***	-0.04**	-0.05***
BFR (issuer) _{<i>j</i>}	-	-	-	-	-0.06***	-0.05***	-0.06***	-0.04***
Multilateral financial resistance								
MFR_{ij}	-	-	-	-	0.09	1.31**	0.12*	2.44***
N	6050	6050	21188	21188	6748	5950	20378	20378
R ²	0.45	0.45	0.91	0.92	0.58	0.55	0.93	0.95
RESET test (χ^2)	9.91*	9.89*	2.75	2.84	28.03*	9.24*	10.65*	6.42
FE: Year	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes

Notes: (a) *, **, and *** denote significance at the 10%, 5% and 1% levels; (b) Dist stands for bilateral distance.; (c) χ^2 refers to the RESET test. * denotes rejection of the null hypothesis of correct model specification at 1% significance.

Table 4: Baseline model. Portfolio bonds data. Nationality principle.

	Remoteness index			Financial resistance		
	OLS	OLS FE	PPML	OLS FE	PPML	PPML FE
Gravity						
$\ln(\text{Dist})_{ij}$	-0.45***	-0.46***	-0.65***	-0.29***	-0.27***	-0.37***
$\ln(\text{GDP})_j$	0.79***	0.79***	0.95***	0.81***	0.78***	1.06***
$\ln(\text{GDP})_i$	0.75***	0.75***	1.09***	0.79***	0.78***	1.08***
Other gravity						
Common language _{ij}	0.60**	0.61**	0.78***	0.97***	0.70***	0.18
Colony _{ij}	0.90***	0.91***	0.26	0.48***	0.81***	0.53***
Remoteness index						
$RI(\text{EXP})_j$	0.04	0.04	0.06*	-	-	-
$RI(\text{IMP})_i$	0.19***	0.19***	0.21***	-	-	-
Bilateral financial resistance						
BFR (investor) _j	-	-	-	-0.08***	-0.07***	-0.06***
BFR (issuer) _i	-	-	-	-0.05***	-0.05***	-0.05***
Multilateral financial resistance						
MFR_{ij}	-	-	-	-0.12**	-0.78	0.24***
N	7258	7258	21188	7734	7185	20378
R ²	0.43	0.44	0.92	0.53	0.50	0.94
RESET test (χ^2)	11.82*	11.77*	0.00	20.14*	11.48*	0.06
FE: Year	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes

Notes: (a) *, ** and *** denote significance at the 10%, 5% and 1% levels; (b) Dist stands for bilateral distance.; (c) χ^2 refers to the RESET test. * denotes rejection of the null hypothesis of correct model specification at 1% significance.

Table 5: Robustness Check. Nationality principle.

	Equity		Bonds	
	GPPML FE	GPPML FE	GPPML FE	GPPML FE
Gravity				
$\ln(\text{Dist})_{ij}$	-0.61***	-0.22***	-0.64***	-0.36***
$\ln(\text{GDP})_j$	0.93***	1.24***	0.94***	1.04***
$\ln(\text{GDP})_i$	1.15***	1.18***	1.09***	1.08***
Other gravity				
Common language $_{ij}$	1.10***	0.64***	0.77**	0.21
Colony $_{ij}$	-0.26	-0.35*	0.29	0.53***
Remoteness index				
$RI(EXP)_j$	-0.09***	–	0.06**	–
$RI(IMP)_i$	0.06	–	0.20***	–
Bilateral financial resistance				
BFR (investor) $_j$	–	-0.05***	–	-0.06***
BFR (issuer) $_i$	–	-0.04***	–	-0.05***
Multilateral financial resistance				
MFR_{ij}	–	2.44***	–	0.43
N	21188	20378	21188	20378
R^2	0.59	0.61	0.62	0.63
Lambda	0.72	0.98***	0.91	1.04***
RESET test (χ^2)	2.33	7.13*	0.02	0.09
FE: Year	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Notes:

(a) *, ** and *** denote significance at the 10%, 5% and 1% levels;

(b) Dist stands for bilateral distance.;

(c) χ^2 refers to the RESET test. * denotes rejection of the null hypothesis of correct model specification at 1% significance.

Table 6: Extended model. Portfolio equity and bonds data. Nationality principle.

	Portfolio Equity		Portfolio Bonds	
	PPML FE	PPML	PPML FE	PPML
Gravity				
$\ln(\text{Dist})_{ij}$	-0.24***	-0.25***	-0.23*	-0.24*
$\ln(\text{GDP})_j$	1.24***	1.04***	1.07***	1.02***
$\ln(\text{GDP})_i$	1.18***	1.15***	1.08***	1.08***
Other gravity				
Common language $_{ij}$	0.63***	0.50***	0.26	0.27
Colony $_{ij}$	-0.32*	-0.09	0.42*	0.44**
Bilateral financial resistance				
BFR (investor) $_j$	-0.05***	-0.04***	-0.06***	-0.06***
BFR (issuer) $_i$	-0.04***	-0.05***	-0.05***	-0.05***
Multilateral financial resistance				
MFR $_{ij}$	2.41***	0.75***	0.69	0.31***
Other gravity variables				
EUdummy $_{ij}$	-0.07	-0.32*	0.41*	0.38*
Global risk	-	-0.06***	-	-0.01
N	20378	20378	20378	20369
R ²	0.95	0.94	0.94	0.95
RESET test (χ^2)	6.72	9.73*	0.30	0.20
FE: Year	Yes	No	Yes	No

Notes: (a) *, ** and *** denote significance at the 10%, 5% and 1% levels; (b) Dist stands for bilateral distance; (c) χ^2 refers to the RESET test. * denotes rejection of the null hypothesis of correct model specification at 1% significance.

Table 7: Portfolio equity data - IMF residence principle.

	Remoteness index				Financial restrictions resistance			
	OLS	OLS FE	PPML	PPML FE	OLS	OLS FE	PPML	PPML FE
Gravity								
$\ln(\text{Dist})_{ij}$	-0.29***	-0.29***	-0.37***	-0.37***	-0.11*	-0.08	-0.20**	-0.20**
$\ln(\text{GDP})_j$	0.68***	0.68***	0.68***	0.69***	0.73***	0.74***	0.71***	0.71***
$\ln(\text{GDP})_i$	0.50***	0.50***	0.57***	0.57***	0.54***	0.54***	0.58***	0.58***
Other gravity								
Common language _{ij}	2.56***	2.56***	1.56***	1.56***	2.35***	2.33***	1.36***	1.36***
Colony _{ij}	-0.27	-0.27	0.30	0.30	-0.03	-0.00	0.05	0.51
Remoteness index								
$RI(\text{EXP})_j$	0.30***	0.30***	0.17***	0.17***	-	-	-	-
$RI(\text{IMP})_i$	0.34***	0.34***	0.34***	0.35***	-	-	-	-
Bilateral financial resistance								
BFR (investor) _j	-	-	-	-	-0.07***	-0.07***	-0.04***	-0.04***
BFR (issuer) _i	-	-	-	-	-0.03***	-0.03***	-0.03***	-0.03***
Multilateral financial resistance								
MFR_{ij}	-	-	-	-	-0.19***	-0.27***	-0.22***	-0.23**
N	17723	17723	28638	28638	17723	17723	28231	28231
R ²	0.32	0.30	0.53	0.54	0.32	0.37	0.55	0.55
RESET test (χ^2)	10.32*	10.30*	4.85	4.53	11.52*	12.09*	3.20	3.10
FE: Year	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes

Notes: (a) *, ** and *** denote significance at the 10%, 5% and 1% levels; (b) Dist stands for bilateral distance.; (c) χ^2 refers to the RESET test. * denotes rejection of the null hypothesis of correct model specification at 1% significance.

Table 8: Portfolio bonds data - IMF residence principle.

	Remoteness index				Financial restrictions resistance			
	OLS	OLS FE	PPML	PPML FE	OLS	OLS FE	PPML	PPML FE
Gravity								
$\ln(\text{Dist})_{ij}$	-0.55***	-0.54***	-0.54***	-0.50***	-0.31***	-0.25***	-0.43***	-0.34***
$\ln(\text{GDP})_j$	0.62***	0.62***	0.62***	0.62***	0.66***	0.67***	0.63***	0.64***
$\ln(\text{GDP})_i$	0.56***	0.56***	0.80***	0.80***	0.63***	0.63***	0.82***	0.83***
Other gravity								
Common language _{ij}	1.89***	1.90***	0.94***	0.97***	1.61***	1.58***	0.66**	0.68***
Colony _{ij}	-0.09	-0.10	0.25	0.23	0.20	0.26	0.48*	0.53*
Remoteness index								
$RI(\text{EXP})_j$	0.36***	0.38***	0.23***	0.26***	-	-	-	-
$RI(\text{IMP})_i$	0.63***	0.67***	0.46***	0.58***	-	-	-	-
Bilateral financial resistance								
$\text{BFR}(\text{investor})_j$	-	-	-	-	-0.07***	-0.07***	-0.04***	-0.54***
$\text{BFR}(\text{issuer})_i$	-	-	-	-	-0.04***	-0.04***	-0.04***	-0.04***
Multilateral financial restrictions resistance								
MFR_{ij}	-	-	-	-	-0.36***	-0.55***	-0.23***	-0.37***
N	20986	20986	29604	29604	20641	20641	29202	29202
R ²	0.39	0.39	0.66	0.66	0.39	0.40	0.66	0.68
RESET test (χ^2)	13.50*	13.44*	0.66	1.16	15.58*	16.06*	0.26	0.33
FE : Year	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes

Notes: (a) *, ** and *** denote significance at the 10%, 5% and 1% levels; (b) Dist stands for bilateral distance.; (c) χ^2 refers to the RESET test. * denotes rejection of the null hypothesis of correct model specification at 1% significance.

Appendix A Additional information

Table A1: EU portfolio equity investment in world tax havens. In millions and %.

Year	Residence princ. position	Nationality princ. position	%
2007	1.278.723	895.089	30%
2008	712.057	507.016	29%
2009	990.563	672.263	32%
2010	1.126.968	727.875	35%
2011	1.046.592	682.021	35%
2012	1.284.487	860.362	33%
2013	1.554.568	1.055.663	32%
2014	1.563.544	1.063.716	32%
2015	1.547.207	1.093.138	29%
2016	1.682.982	1.228.221	27%
2017	2.295.295	1.639.746	29%

Notes: (a) Tax havens included in the table are listed in table A3; (b) residence principle position data comes from the IMF CPIS, whereas Nationality principle position data comes from the database by Coppola et al. (2021).

Table A2: USA portfolio equity investment in EU tax havens. In millions and %.

Year	Residence princ. position	Nationality princ. position	%
2007	216.360	174.337	19%
2008	97.031	79.987	18%
2009	196.728	131.029	33%
2010	232.155	144.959	38%
2011	216.822	137.157	37%
2012	275.693	166.405	40%
2013	459.257	278.643	39%
2014	555.426	297.192	46%
2015	654.096	314.308	52%
2016	634.047	329.483	48%
2017	758.898	425.398	44%

Notes:

(a) EU tax havens are Cyprus, Ireland, Luxembourg, Malta, and Netherlands. (b): residence principle position data comes from the IMF CPIS, whereas nationality principle position data comes from the database by Coppola et al. (2021).

Table A3: List of tax havens

Country	Country
Aruba	Saint Kitts and Nevis
Anguilla	Lebanon
Andorra	Liberia
Netherlands Antilles	Saint Lucia
Antigua and Barbuda	Liechtenstein
Bahrain	Luxembourg
Bahamas	Macao
Belize	Monaco
Bermuda	Maldives
Barbados	Marshall Islands
Cook Islands	Malta
Costa Rica	Montserrat
Curaçao	Mauritius
Cayman Islands	Niue
Cyprus	Netherlands
Djibouti	Nauru
Dominica	Panama
Micronesia, Federated States of	Singapore
Guernsey	San Marino
Gibraltar	Seychelles
Grenada	Turks and Caicos Islands
Hong Kong	Tonga
Isle of Man	Saint Vincent and the Grenadines
Ireland	Virgin Islands, British
Jersey	Vanuatu
Jordan	Samoa

Source: Coppola et al. (2021)

Table A4: Countries in the sample. Equity

Investor	Period
Argentina, Bahrain, Bermuda, Brazil, Bulgaria, Canada, Cayman Islands, Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica Czech Republic, Denmark, Egypt, European Monetary Union, Hong Kong, Hungary, Iceland, India Indonesia, Israel, Japan, Kazakhstan, Korea, Republic of, Kuwait, Lebanon, Macao Malaysia, Mauritius, Mexico, New Zealand, Pakistan, Panama, Philippines, Poland Romania, Russian Federation, Singapore, South Africa, Sweden, Switzerland, Thailand Turkey, Ukraine, United Kingdom, United States, Uruguay	2007-2017
Mongolia	2010-2017
Bolivia	2011-2017
Saudi Arabia	2013-2017
Bangladesh, Belarus, Honduras, Norway	2014-2017
Albania, China, Peru	2015-2017
Macedonia	2016-2017
Australia	2017
Issuer	Period
Afghanistan, Albania, Algeria, Angola, Antigua and Barbuda, Argentina, Armenia, Aruba, Australia Austria, Azerbaijan, Bahamas, Bahrain, Bangladesh, Barbados, Belarus, Belgium, Belize, Benin Bermuda, Bhutan, Bolivia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Botswana, Brazil, Brunei Darussalam, Bulgaria Burkina Faso, Burundi, Cambodia, Cameroon, Canada, Cape Verde, Cayman Islands, Central African Republic Chad, Chile, China, Colombia, Comoros, Congo, Costa Rica, Côte d' Ivoire, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic Denmark, Dominica, Dominican Republic, Ecuador, Egypt, El Salvador, Equatorial Guinea, Estonia Ethiopia, Fiji, Finland, France, Gambia, Georgia, Germany, Ghana, Greece, Grenada Guatemala, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Guyana, Haiti, Honduras, Hong Kong, Hungary, Iceland India, Indonesia, Iran, Islamic Republic of, Iraq, Ireland, Israel, Italy, Jamaica, Japan, Jordan, Kazakhstan Kenya, Kiribati, Korea, Republic of, Kuwait, Kyrgyzstan, Lao People's Democratic Republic, Latvia, Lebanon Lesotho, Liberia, Libya, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Macao, Macedonia, Madagascar, Malawi, Malaysia Maldives, Mali, Malta, Marshall Islands, Mauritania, Mauritius, Mexico, Micronesia, Federated States of Moldova Republic of, Mongolia, Morocco, Mozambique, Myanmar, Namibia, Nepal, Netherlands New Zealand, Nicaragua, Niger, Nigeria, Norway, Oman, Pakistan, Palau, Panama, Papua New Guinea Paraguay, Peru, Philippines, Poland, Portugal, Qatar, Romania, Russian Federation, Rwanda, Saint Kitts and Nevis Saint Lucia, Saint Vincent and the Grenadines, Samoa, Sao Tome and Principe, Saudi Arabia, Senegal, Seychelles Sierra Leone, Singapore, Slovakia, Slovenia, Solomon Islands, South Africa, Spain, Sri Lanka, Sudan, Suriname Swaziland, Sweden, Switzerland, Syrian Arab Republic, Tajikistan, Tanzania, United Republic of, Thailand, Togo Tonga, Trinidad and Tobago, Tunisia, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Uganda, Ukraine, United Arab Emirates United Kingdom, United States, Uruguay, Uzbekistan, Vanuatu, Vietnam, Yemen, Zambia, Zimbabwe	2007-2017
Eritrea	2007-2011
Djibouti	2013-2017

Table A5: Countries in the sample.Bonds

Investor	Period
Argentina, Bahrain, Bermuda, Brazil, Bulgaria, Canada, Cayman Islands, Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, Czech Republic, Denmark Egypt, European Monetary Union, Korea, Republic of, Kuwait, Lebanon, Macao, Malaysia, Mauritius, Mexico New Zealand, Pakistan, Panama, Philippines, Poland, Romania, Russian Federation, Singapore, South Africa Sweden, Switzerland, Thailand, Turkey, Ukraine, United Kingdom, United States, Uruguay	2007-2017
Bahamas	2007-2014
Barbados	2007-2015
Mongolia	2010-2017
Bolivia	2011-2017
Saudi Arabia	2013-2017
Bangladesh, Belarus, Honduras, Norway	2014-2017
Albania, China, Peru	2015-2017
Australia	2017
Bahrain	2007-2011
Aruba, United Kingdom	2007-2016
Macedonia	2016-2017
Issuer	Period
Afghanistan, Albania, Algeria, Angola, Antigua and Barbuda, Argentina, Armenia, Aruba, Australia, Austria, Azerbaijan Bahamas, Bahrain, Bangladesh, Belgium, Belize, Benin, Bermuda, Bhutan, Bolivia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Botswana, Brazil Brunei Darussalam, Bulgaria, Burkina Faso, Burundi, Cambodia, Cameroon, Canada, Cape Verde, Cayman Islands Central African Republic, Chad, Chile, China, Colombia, Comoros, Congo, Democratic Republic of the Cost Rica, Croatia, Cyprus Czech Republic, Denmark, Dominica, Dominican Republic, Ecuador, Egypt, El Salvador, Equatorial Guinea, Côte d'Ivoire Estonia, Ethiopia, Fiji, Finland, France, Gabon, Gambia, Georgia, Germany, Ghana, Greece, Grenada, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau Guyana, Haiti, Honduras, Hong Kong, Hungary, Iceland, India, Indonesia, Iran, Islamic Republic of, Iraq, Ireland, Israel, Italy Jamaica, Japan, Jordan, Kazakhstan, Kenya, Kiribati, Korea, Republic of Kuwait, Kyrgyzstan, Lao People's Dem. Republic Latvia, Lebanon, Lesotho, Liberia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Macao, Macedonia, Madagascar, Malawi, Malaysia, Maldives Mali, Malta, Marshall Islands, Mauritius, Mexico, Micronesia, Moldova, Mongolia, Morocco, Mozambique, Myanmar Namibia, Nepal, Netherlands, New Zealand, Nicaragua, Niger, Nigeria, Norway, Oman, Pakistan, Palau, Panama, Papua New Guinea Paraguay, Peru, Philippines, Poland, Portugal, Qatar, Romania, Russian Federation, Rwanda, Saint Kitts and Nevis, Saint Lucia Saint Vincent and the Grenadines, Samoa, Sao Tome and Principe, Saudi Arabia, Senegal, Singapore, Seychelles, Sierra Leone Slovakia, Slovenia, Solomon Islands, South Africa, Spain, Sri Lanka, Sudan, Suriname, Sweden, Switzerland, Syrian Arab Republic Tajikistan, Tanzania, United Republic of, Thailand, Togo, Tonga, Trinidad and Tobago, Tunisia, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Uganda Ukraine, United Arab Emirates, United Kingdom, United States, Uruguay, Uzbekistan, Vanuatu, Vietnam, Yemen, Zambia, Zimbabwe	2007-2017
Djibouti	2013-2017
Eritrea	2007-2011